

Photolysis of Amino Acids in Sunlight.

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From the standpoint of soil fertility the nitrogenous portion of the soil is of paramount importance. Most of the nitrogen added to the soil by ploughing under sod, plant stubble, green and stable manure, is in the form of proteins and their decomposition products. These substances cannot be assimilated by higher plants as such, but have to be broken down to ammonia and then oxidised to nitrate. The nitrates are then assimilated by the plants.

It was at first thought that organic matter can be nitrified directly. But, Muntz (*Compt. rend.*, 1890, 110, 1206) has shown that organic matter has to be decomposed first and ammonia liberated, before nitrates can be formed. Omeliansky (*Cent. Bakt.*, 1899, 5, 473; 1902, 9, 63) also obtained negative results for urea, asparagine, methylamine and egg-albumin; so that he concluded that all forms of organic nitrogen have to be transformed first into ammonia before they can be nitrified and utilised by the plant. The decomposition of organic nitrogenous compounds with the liberation of ammonia is commonly known as ammonification. From what has been said above it will be evident that ammonification is an important chemical process occurring in the soil.

The isolation of a number of amino acids from the soils by Schreiner and Shorey (*U.S. Dept. Agr. Bur. Soils Bull. No. 74*) and Lathrop (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 34, 1260) has demonstrated that the process of decay of proteins takes place through the stage of amino acids. The amino acids give rise to ammonia by further processes of hydrolysis and oxidation.

Muntz (*loc. cit.*) was the first to demonstrate that organic nitrogenous matter is decomposed by micro-organisms with the formation of ammonia. Muntz and Coudon (*Compt. rend.*, 1893, 116, 395) have further shown that no ammonia was formed in sterile soil in two

and half years, while the unsterilised soil produced in sixty seven days 41 to 100 mg. of ammonia per 100 g. of soil. These investigations were followed by those of Marchall (*Cent. Bakt.*, 1895, 2, 753) and numerous others which pointed out the importance of ammonia formation in the soil and the rôle of micro-organisms in its formation from proteins. This was found to be not a specific property of certain bacteria, but a function of a large number of micro-organisms and fungi.

In the light of the above experimental evidence it is believed that ammonification in soils is solely due to the action of bacteria and fungi. It is important to observe that the experiments of all those investigators were conducted in the dark. Now the present authors have studied the decomposition of various nitrogenous compounds like amino acids, amides, amines, proteins, etc., in aqueous solution in the presence of sunlight and photocatalysts like titanium dioxide, aluminium trioxide, humic acid, zinc oxide, etc. These experiments have revealed that most nitrogenous compounds are decomposed into ammonia, which may then be oxidised to nitrite, and nitrate and in a recent communication (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 699) it has been shown that light not only plays an important rôle in nitrification but it is of great importance to ammonification, which is mainly an oxidation reaction. In this paper the influence of light on the oxidation of some amino acids has been investigated in the absence of bacteria.

The amino acids are oxidised to ammonia, carbon dioxide and an aldehyde containing one carbon atom less. The change can be represented by the equation,

We have also observed that the rate of photo-oxidation of amino acids is greater than that of ammonia to nitrate. Hence there is less likelihood for the simultaneous formation of nitrite in the experiments on photo-ammonification, specially in view of the fact that no air was passed through the exposed solutions continuously. Besides, it has been shown in publications from these laboratories that reducing substances act as negative catalysts in oxidation reactions. The aldehyde formed in the photo-oxidation of amino acid would, therefore, inhibit the further oxidation of ammonia to nitrite. Thus in our experiments we have observed the formation of only traces of nitrite.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The amino acids used in this investigation were obtained from Kahlbaum. The requisite amount of the amino acid was dissolved in sterile water and the solution poured into a sterile Erlenmeyer flask of pyrex glass containing a definite amount of photosensitiser and then plugged with sterile cotton wool. Thereafter the flask was exposed to sunlight. An exactly similar flask was kept in the dark as a blank and every precaution was taken to avoid bacterial contamination in these light and dark experiments. The blank solution did not develop any ammonia, while the one exposed to sunlight showed a steady increase in the amount of ammonia formed. The non-formation of ammonia in the dark (blank) solution shows the freedom from contamination of the experimental solutions with any ammonifying organisms.

Methods of analysis.—The determination of ammonia was done by the improved Folin aeration method, using sodium carbonate to liberate the ammonia. The residual amino-nitrogen was determined by the van Slyke method.

Glycine.—250 C.c. of a solution of *M*/20-aminoacetic acid were exposed to sunlight with and without photosensitiser under strictly aseptic conditions. There is a slow but definite oxidative decomposition in sunlight in glass vessels without any photosensitiser. In quartz vessels the decomposition is more rapid. The photolysis in the presence of photosensitisers, like titanium dioxide, is considerably more rapid; hence this photosensitised oxidation was studied in greater detail. Analysis of the reaction products has shown that the actual decomposition of the amino acid can be represented as

The amount of ammonia-nitrogen formed was estimated by the Folin aeration method; and the amount of amino-nitrogen disappeared has been determined by the well known van Slyke method. The following results show that the amount of NH_3 -nitrogen corresponds almost quantitatively to the decrease in the NH_2 -N. The following table shows the progress of the photolysis of glycine with time in the presence of titanium dioxide.

TABLE I.

250 C.c. of *M*/20-glycine + 0.25 g. of TiO_2 exposed in a glass flask to sunlight for 80 hours.

NH ₂ -N in g./10 c.c.		Diff. decrease in NH ₂ -N.	Folin NH ₂ -N.
Before. irradiation.	After		
0.006980	0.005817	0.001163	0.001160

TABLE II.

250 C.c. of *M*/20-glycine + 0.25 g. of TiO_2 exposed to sunlight in a glass flask. Amount of NH₂-N per litre = 698 mg.

Time (hr.)	...	40	80	120	160
NH ₂ -N (mg./litre)	...	28.82	115.28	185.00	244.30
Decomposition (%)	...	4.13	16.50	26.64	35.00

Under the conditions of the experiment only minute traces of nitrite were formed.

Photodecomposition of anthranilic acid.—*M*/20-solution of anthranilic acid (*o*-aminobenzoic acid) was exposed to sunlight in a pyrex glass flask with titanium dioxide, under conditions which excluded bacterial contamination. After a few hours' exposure the solution assumed a deep red-brown colour. Analysis revealed the presence of aniline. It appears, therefore, that preliminary decomposition of anthranilic acid can be represented by the equation,

Prolonged exposure resulted in the formation of ammonia which was estimated by the Folin aeration method. The results are recorded in the following table.

TABLE III.

250 C. c. of M/20-amino acids with 0.25 g. of catalyst were exposed to the sun in a glass flask under sterile conditions. 20 C. c. portions were withdrawn from time to time and ammonia liberated was estimated by Folin's method.

Amino acids.	Time of exposure.									
	40 hrs.	80 hrs.	120 hrs.	160 hrs.	200 hrs.					
	NH ₃ -N decom- (mg./litre). position.									
Glycine + TiO ₂	28.82	4.13 %	115.28	16.5%	185.00	26.64%	244.3	35%
Alanine + TiO ₂	43.23	6.2	86.5	12.40	129.80	18.76	217.54	31.20%
Alanine + ZnO	160.21	23.01	319.32	45.80	478.56	68.66
Alanine + Al ₂ O ₃	4.50	0.645	9.21	1.3	13.7	1.96	19.4	2.78
Aspartic acid + TiO ₂	25.22	3.6	50.48	7.23	75.60	10.83	125.00	17.90
Aspartic acid + ZnO	71.29	10.21	142.10	20.3	213.42	30.57
Asparagine + TiO ₂	50.44	3.61	115.28	8.26	172.13	12.7
Glutamic acid + TiO ₂	25.22	3.6	50.44	7.2	75.64	10.84	124.60	17.82

TABLE IV.

250 C. c. *M*/20-anthranilic acid + 0.25 g. of TiO₂ exposed to sunlight.

Time (hr.)	40	80	120
NH ₃ -N formed (mg./litre).	14.41	21.61	27.76
Decomposition %	2.06	3.09	4.12

Hippuric acid is very stable in sunlight even in the presence of photosensitisers.

SUMMARY.

1. The photolysis of various amino acids in sunlight has been studied. These amino acids decompose with the liberation of ammonia. The decomposition appears to be one of oxidative de-amination. The aliphatic amino acids, *e.g.*, glycine are oxidised in the presence of air and sunlight with the formation of the corresponding aldehyde, ammonia and carbon dioxide. This is represented by the general equation,

2. In most of the cases, the amount of ammoniacal nitrogen formed by photolysis was found to correspond quantitatively to the decrease in amino-nitrogen.

3. From the experimental results it will be seen that monoamino-dicarboxylic acids like aspartic acid and glutamic acid ammonify less readily than the monoaminomonocarboxylic acid like glycine and alanine. It will also be seen that aromatic amino acids like anthranilic acid and hippuric acid, ammonify much less readily than the aliphatic ones.

4. In the light of the above experimental evidence, the authors believe that the formation of ammonia in the soil from amino acids obtained from protein decomposition is mainly an oxidative de-amination, accelerated by sunlight. We have shown that aqueous solutions of amino acids photolyse in the presence of photosensitisers like titanium dioxide, aluminium oxide, humic acid, zinc oxide, etc., when we keep in mind that the first three substances normally occur in all soils it will be clear that ammonification in soils can take place without the presence of bacteria or fungi, if only sunlight be present.